

Implementation of a community of inquiry in teaching English as a foreign language in secondary schools: A literature review

Suharno Suharno, Didi Suherdi, Wawan Gunawan

English Education Study Program, Faculty of Language and Literature Education, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Bandung, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received May 12, 2022
Revised Aug 24, 2023
Accepted Sep 20, 2023

Keywords:

Cognitive presence
Community of inquiry
Distance learning
Social presence
Teaching presence

ABSTRACT

Garrison, Anderson, and Archer's community of inquiry (CoI) pedagogical framework for online distance learning is receiving greater attention as the COVID-19 takes place. Primary research concerns the researcher with English as a second language (ESL) instruction and acquisition English as a foreign language (EFL). More specifically, the study looked at 27 EFL-related articles from 133 published between 2011 and 2021 in respected journals that used the framework to teach languages. This study focused on the theoretical and practical applications of the framework in the field of foreign language distance teaching and learning that incorporates the use of information and communication of technology (ICT). It was concluded from the study's findings that implementing the framework in secondary schools had little impact. Research suggests that the framework can be used in teaching English as foreign language (TEFL) and it is associated with improved language proficiency. Teachers must adapt to the distant learning pedagogical framework and its supporting technology, according to this study. The paper also advocates for further research into how the framework may be applied in secondary school.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Suharno Suharno
English Education Study Program, Faculty of Language and Literature Education
Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia
Dr. Setiabudi Street No. 229, Bandung, Indonesia
Email: suharno@upi.edu

1. INTRODUCTION

Approaches, methods, and tactics for teaching and learning English as a foreign language (EFL) have changed over time. It used to be grammar-translation (GTM) and audio-lingual that were the most often employed, but as time went on, a more natural and meaningful one emerged, and in the last decade, new approaches and methodologies emerged, such as genre-based, science, technology, engineering, art, and math (STEAM), scientific approach, and others. Prior to the outbreak, these techniques were employed in the classroom, a physical location where teachers and students can converse face-to-face with each other (also better known as a traditional classroom). Coronavirus pandemic or COVID-19, which is affecting schooling around the world, caused an unexpected turn in events. Schools and universities were closed, and classes were delivered entirely online. Teachers and students may be separated geographically and chronologically, but technology allows them to communicate virtually. Teaching EFL in an entirely new setting, such as an online classroom, necessitates that EFL instructors learn how to use new methods and strategies (VLE).

As a result of a sudden shift from face-to-face to distant learning, there are both positive and negative aspects to consider. Teachers and students face difficulties adapting to new forms of instruction due to a lack of internet access and a lack of proficiency in digital literacy [1]. Researchers found that professors

were unfamiliar with distant learning pedagogy [2]. It has been shown that the benefits of this new method of teaching (online and blended, also called hybrid or flipped) include time and space efficiency. As long as both teachers and students have access to the internet, instructions can take place at any time and in any location. Additionally, students can avoid the dangers of being away from their families. Distance learning has a bright future thanks to the rapid advancements being made in digital technology, open-source software communities, and application development tools. Learning new skills and knowledge in the digital age can be accomplished through online education, which is universally accepted as an effective means for students to do so [3]. Learning challenges and possibilities, however, necessitate ongoing research in order to find new and better ways of teaching and learning [4].

For distant education, the community of inquiry or CoI framework [5]–[12] is used in many of ways [5]–[12]. These studies show that the framework's use in teaching English as foreign language (TEFL) has produced beneficial effects for teachers and students alike. In TEFL instruction, it is obvious that CoI is a powerful technique to foster involvement in a learning community that results in a positive outcome. However, studies on the adoption of CoI in TEFL have thus far been confined to higher education institutions and rarely reported on in secondary schools. Research conducted in high schools indicated a strong association between the deployment of CoI and the increase of English language competency [12]. Using the CoI framework to teach four English language skills in secondary education is achievable because of this feature.

However, previous to the pandemic, distance learning had been used on a limited level, particularly in higher institutions. Only to supplement or scaffold face-to-face training was it implemented. It has taken some time for the new mode to take hold. A single mode of transportation was all that was available when schools were shut down due to a pandemic. Remote education was critical in halting the spread of the virus. These include, for example, whether or if there are pedagogical frameworks (frameworks) applicable to distance learning, whether or not the framework is applicable to language learning, and how the framework is implemented in EFL distant instruction.

2. SELECTION PROCESS

The data used were only empirical peer-reviewed h-indexed research articles published in English. Although related information in the form of journal articles was predominantly searched in Google Scholar during the selection process, the study also included significant triangulation and comparison of results from a number of other scholarly publishing sources. Other databases that had articles found in Google Scholar were ScienceGate, Researchgate, ProQuest, EBSCO, Web of Science, ERIC, and ScienceDirect. Some articles were also obtained from the websites of the CoI. The research journals that were compiled to support the literature review were related to the theoretical and practical foundation of the community of inquiry framework and the three succeeding dimensions of social, cognitive, and teaching presences. The selection process started with the idea of CoI for all disciplines, then moved on to education, language acquisition, and finally EFL. The keywords community of inquiry, social presence, cognitive presence, and teaching presence were used in the search. The journal articles for this review must have been published between 2011 and 2021. Table 1 and Figure 1 provide the inclusion and exclusion criteria, as well as a flowchart of the selection process.

Table 1. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Focus of the article	Community of inquiry in EFL distance learning	Articles that did not focus on community of inquiry in EFL distance learning
Publication type	Scholarly peer-reviewed research journals	Non-scholarly peer-reviewed research journals
Publication date	2011-2021	Prior to 2011 and after 2021
Research method & result	Quantitative and qualitative, there was identifiable methods and result section	Articles that do not include methods, procedure, or data analysis
Language	English	Other than English

The search managed to find 3.202 (n=3.202) journal articles related to community of inquiry for all disciplines. The next step was filtering the articles in the areas of language teaching-learning and found 133 articles. The final stage was to exclude those irrelevant to EFL teaching and learning. Through this inclusion, 27 articles related to CoI with the tree dimensions of presences were selected. Yearly CoI-related language learning and EFL publication is illustrated in Table 2.

Figure 1. Flowchart of selection process

Table 2. Publications related to CoI framework

Publication year	CoI framework related to language teaching and learning	CoI framework related to EFL teaching and learning
2021	19	5
2020	25	6
2019	16	3
2018	15	3
2017	14	2
2016	14	1
2015	11	2
2014	6	1
2013	2	0
2012	4	3
2011	7	1
Sum	133	27

3. THE FRAMEWORK OF COMMUNITY OF INQUIRY (CoI)

Garrison *et al.* [13] invented the CoI framework. It is a theoretical framework that explains how to create three interdependent elements (social, cognitive, and teaching presence) in order to create a deep and meaningful (collaborative-constructivist) learning experience. This notion considers the social and cognitive dimensions of student participation in the creation of knowledge [14]. Cognitive presence refers to students' ability to construct meaning and build understanding, social presence refers to students' ability to present themselves as "real people" with distinct characteristics, and teaching presence refers to the design and facilitation of cognitive and social presences to achieve learning outcomes. Effective remote instruction, according to the CoI paradigm, is the outcome of well designed and enabled interactions between educational resources, students, and teachers [15]. It has been shown to be a useful theoretical framework and tool for researching and designing online learning experiences [16].

CoI is particularly common in online learning communities, which are groups of people that are engaging in a collaborative, open, participatory, and flexible learning project [17]. It is a community that evolved as a result of the educational paradigm shift from knowledge transmission to knowledge construction, from a teacher-centered method to a student-centered approach, and from passive learning to participatory learning [18]. Virtual learning communities, in this sense, are a participatory network that promotes communication, the exchange of ideas, and the socialization of experiences that lead to personal and communal identity, and thus to the development of knowledge. Figure 2 depicts the three presences as multidimensional elements. The constituent categories, as observed, are employed to operationalize each of the presences. Social presence is defined as affective expression, open communication, and group cohesion; while teaching presence is defined as design, facilitation, and direct instruction as shown in Table 3.

Figure 2. CoI

Table 3. Operational definitions of the presences [19]

Element	Categories	Indicators (examples only)
Social presence	Open communication	Learning climate/risk-free expression
	Group cohesion	Group identity/collaboration
Cognitive presence	Personal/affective	Self-projection/expressing emotions
	Triggering event	Sense of puzzlement
	Exploration	Information exchange
	Integration	Connecting ideas
Teaching presence	Resolution	Applying new ideas
	Design and organization	Setting curriculum & methods
	Facilitating discourse	Setting constructive exchange
	Direct instruction	Focusing and resolving issues

3.1. Social presence

Garrison [20] in 2009 describes social presence as the ability of participants in a community of inquiry to project themselves socially and emotionally, as “real” individuals (i.e., their entire personality), through the medium of communication used. He refines decisively in a trusted environment, and develop interpersonal relationships by projecting their individual personalities in order to rationalize the conceptualization of social presence with the conceptualizations of the other presences. Garrison *et al.* [13] in 2001 defines social presence as the i) Group cohesion (reflecting the community’s shared social identity and collaborative behavioral intention); ii) Open communication (expressing the community’s common social identity and joint behavioral goal); and iii) Affective expression (reflecting the socio-emotional aspects of communication in order to create interpersonal ties). Vocatives are words or phrases used to address a reader or listener directly, usually in the form of a personal name, title, or term of endearment. Then open communication can be realized by maintaining a thread, referencing from others’ messages, directly referring to others’ messages, asking questions and receiving feedback, flattering or voicing appreciation, and agreeing. Finally, affective expression includes emotional expression (e.g., usage of emoticons, noticeable capitalization), comedy, and openness (e.g., providing personal information, displaying vulnerability). According to Garrison [20], the various types of this operationalization of social presence can be viewed as stages of a process in which a shared social identity derived from the course’s purpose is the primary concern at first, and then serves as the foundation for the establishment of interpersonal ties later. According to Garrison [20], Sunga and Mayer’s study of social presence [21] reveals five aspects of social presence in an online learning environment: i) Social respect (e.g., responding on time); ii) Social sharing (e.g., sharing information or expressing views); iii) Open mind (e.g., expressing agreement or giving encouraging feedback); iv) Social identity (e.g., addressed by name); and v) Intimacy (e.g., sharing personal experiences).

3.2. Cognitive presence

Cognitive presence is defined as the investigation, construction, resolution, and validation of understanding in a community of inquiry through cooperation and reflection [22]. In this context, cognitive presence is operationalized into four critical inquiry phases: i) Triggering event-the initial identification of issues for further investigation; ii) Exploration-the collaborative investigation of issues via critical discourse; iii) Integration-the construction of meaning based on the idea exchanged in the exploration phase; and iv) Resolution-the resolution of dilemmas or issues through direct or indirect actions. When students can link concepts, apply new ideas, define the curriculum, set the climate for learning, and inject knowledge from various sources, their cognitive presence improves.

The following are tips for establishing cognitive presence in a virtual learning environment culled from several sources, including [23]–[27]: i) Provide a variety of exercises for students to practice desired skills; ii) Utilize words and images to teach topics concurrently; iii) Start with the end objective in mind; iv) Clearly convey to students what they will learn in class; v) Provide pupils with a variety of assignments from which to demonstrate their learning; vi) Offer a variety of content and activities, such as video, writing, audio, reflection, group work, readings, games, and so on; vii) Provide several opportunities for low-stakes formative evaluation; viii) Promote introspection; ix) Develop conversation starters and delve deeply into engaged debates; x) Use roleplaying exercises to demonstrate a variety of themes; xi) Have students lead discussions; xii) Develop group projects in which students collaborate; provide opportunities for peer review with explicit rubrics for evaluation; xiii) Relate existing to previous learning content; xiv) Encourage pupils to consider what they are learning now and how they will apply this knowledge in the future; xv) Foster diverse standpoints and discussion to comprehend those perspectives; xvi) Encourage pupils to think about what they are studying now and how they will use what they have learned in the future; xvii) Provide example and support various points of view in online interactions; xviii) Provide occasions for group brainstorming, such as designing concept maps together; xix) Provide opportunities for vision into how others are thinking through tools such as polling, breakout rooms, or team assignments; xx) Develop grading rubrics that clearly indicate the quality of different answers and the corresponding scoring; xxi) Post examples of accomplished assignments; xxi) Have students complete assignments; and xxi) Offers several possibilities for input and testing.

3.3. Teaching presence

According to Anderson *et al.* [28], teaching presence is the design, facilitation, and direction of (student) cognitive and social presences for the purpose of realizing personally meaningful and educationally worthwhile learning outcomes. There are three unique components to the teaching presence (instructional design and organization, discourse facilitation, and direct instructional acts). Teaching presence is defined as the “binding element” that brings together an online learning community and facilitates the cognitive and social activities essential for successful online learning [29]. A thorough evaluation of the three components of teaching presence yields specific advice for remote teachers.

Teaching presence begins before any interactions with students with the design and arrangement of an online course [16]. Decisions about course objectives, schedules, and syllabi reflect the teacher’s role as the principal designer and administrator of students’ learning experiences [30]. Teachers, for example, should develop explicit learning objectives and link learning activities to assessments to appropriately manage this duty. This can assist students in navigating a course and deriving meaning from learning resources. Teachers can also help facilitate student conversation. Learning outcomes improve when students may actively engage in collaborative dialogs with other peers or classmates through discussions that personalize, question, and expand on ideas taught in class. To put it another way, teachers play a critical role in promoting healthy dialogue by restricting class discussions, suggesting relevant themes, identifying points of agreement and controlling student participation [31]. Lastly, for a successful teaching presence in an online learning environment, effective and regular use of direct instruction is essential. Teachers who exercise scholarly leadership participate in direct instruction through logical subject presentation and the injection of internal resources/points of view, as well as evaluative duties such as testing students’ understanding or offering feedback [29]. It is critical to highlight that teacher-student involvement does not require synchronicity. According to research, students benefit from distant learning in an effective asynchronous mode more than those who require regular synchronous encounters [32].

Creating an online teaching presence takes more time to prepare than creating a classroom presence. However, with a successful online course design, instructors can develop and retain their presence, as well as their discipline expertise, while also providing their students with a beneficial learning experience. Adapted from various sources, especially from [28], [33], [34], Table 4 shows suggestions on a number of techniques to create and maintain effective teaching presence.

Table 4. Elements of teaching presence

Design	Facilitating discourse	Direct instruction
1. Deliver specific learning goals	1. Begin the course with a discourse that builds trust (for example, introductions and icebreakers)	1. Provide specific ideas/share professional and scholarly knowledge
2. Provide the course outline and welcome message	2. Outline the standards for discussion participation (duration, topic, expectations, netiquette, and timelessness)	2. Assist students in correcting mistakes and diagnosing understanding
3. Hold an initial synchronous meeting to introduce the speaker and course	3. Encourage good dialogue by asking engaging/open-ended questions	3. Recommend new resources/content; incorporate expertise from outside sources
4. Make certain that the instructions for performing course activities and using essential technology are clear	4. Put pupils' ideas to the test (ask for justification/rationale)	4. Make abstract notions concrete by connecting ideas (analogies/related themes)
5. Establish course participation and activity expectations for students	5. Monitor the debate to guarantee fruitful dialogue and, as needed, shape the path	5. Share personal experiences and feedback on the lecturers' own efforts to master content
6. Communicate assignment deadlines and remind students frequently as deadlines approach	6. Create a model of suitable contributions	6. Give frequent feedback and evaluation advice
7. Provide chances for active learning that are engaging, relevant, and appropriate.	7. Concentrate on the pupil making meaning and reinforcing understanding	7. Deliver content in an efficient and targeted manner
8. Create assessments that are aligned with learning objectives	8. Foster informally and receptivity to all viewpoints	8. Provide probing inquiries that elicit reflection and cognitive dissonance
9. Explain lecturer engagement expectations (e.g., extent of lecturer participation in class discussions and email response times)	9. Locate points of controversy	9. As needed, scaffold student comprehension
10. Deliver information in a conversational instead of scholarly tone	10. Reinforces and encourages engagement (attracts less active participants while tempering more active posters)	10. Personalize and add interest to given scholarly work by annotating/commenting on it
	11. Find common ground/agree/summarize class topics	
	12. Discuss personal meanings and experiences	

4. DEVELOPMENT OF CoI FRAMEWORK

Initial work of Garrison *et al.* [13] resulting in establishment of CoI framework with three interdependent presences was then followed by expanding each presence, their relationship and interdependences [28], [13]. The framework became guiding principle for researchers for further exploration [31], [35] and instructors to make up-to-date educational decisions [36], [37]. Based on CoI framework, Fiock [38] created a practical guide to design online courses that aligns with good practice principles [39].

Arbaugh *et al.* [40] created a 34-item reliable, valid, and efficient instrument to assess the CoI framework's dimensions. This instrument drew researchers away from content analysis of online discussions and toward an online survey utilizing the CoI instrument. According to Stenbom [36], the researchers' goals in using the CoI instrument were to investigate a single learning environment, examine differences using the CoI survey, observe relationships between the different elements of CoI and their relationships with other data, and address data reliability and/or validity using the CoI survey. Furthermore, researchers revealed causal links and correlations between the presences and other factors while utilizing the instrument [36]. Teaching presence (TP) scores distinctly predict cognitive presence (CP) and social presence (SP) perceptions [41]. According to Lin *et al.* [42], CP improves. Lin *et al.* [42] also revealed that CP improves training effectiveness.

Researchers, like Rourke and Kanuka [43] and Akyol *et al.* [19], began to attack the CoI framework, stating that learners do not acquire meaningful learning in the CoI and that the CoI is a process framework that informs on instructional approaches rather than learning outcomes. To be more useful as a framework, the CoI framework requires additional components. Shea *et al.* [44] suggested learner presence, emotional presence [45], and autonomous presence in response to the critique [46]. None of the extra frameworks for the three presences, however, have been validated [47].

One of the most often utilized frameworks in online instruction is the CoI framework [48]. Researchers are still urged to collaborate with K-12 [49], industry [50], and mixed learning environments [51]. Furthermore, research on disciplinary distinctions using the CoI framework is required [52]. Replication and modification can assist you have a thorough understanding of the subject.

5. FRAMEWORK OF COMMUNITY INQUIRY IN EFL INSTRUCTION

To begin with, compared to journal publications of articles related to the CoI framework in general, the publication of frameworks related to language learning, particularly EFL, is much less. There have only been 27 related to the EFL compared to 3,202 related to other disciplines in the last 10 years as shown in Table 4. This could be due to the fact that the CoI framework is widely accepted across all fields. This means that when considering online learning in different areas, it will most likely apply to English learning. According to the theory, meaningful online distance learning is intimately tied to the fulfillment of three

presences (social, cognitive, and teaching presence) [28]. As Sallán [53] confirmed, CoI is the most ubiquitous in a virtual learning community, which is a group of people involved in a collaborative, open, participatory, and flexible learning initiative. CoI framework is a collaborative-constructivist process model that describes the essential elements of a successful online higher education learning experience [54].

Like in other disciplines, in English language learning the achievement of course goals and objectives, as well as mastery of content, are paramount in the virtual language learning environment. What online teachers have to strive for the success of their student's language learning is by fostering online interaction and collaboration among course participants. Application of CoI framework with the three presences in online distance language learning is relevant for this purpose.

Cognitive online presence is vital for achieving fundamental cognitive learning and engaging students through effective teaching. Facilitating interaction and overt teaching practice can help with this. To attain these goals, learners must emphasize self-efficacy, self-regulation, and a strong emphasis on inquiry [55]. Educators and researchers have discovered that online communication centered on language learning and teaching improves learning and cognitive presence [56]. Online conversation, discussion opportunities, reflection papers, journaling, and reactions to readings and video clips are the primary online techniques aimed to modify cognitive presence. Each exercise is accompanied with a rubric and assessment structure, as well as on-time feedback and grading.

To attain these goals, learners must emphasize self-efficacy, autonomy, and a strong emphasis on inquiry [55]. Prior to the start of the course, students receive a clear indication of the instructor's commitment and expertise in developing a course for the online learning environment that focuses on cognitive presence, engagement, and positive on-time feedback, which includes course design, goals and objectives, rigorous and engaging modules. When students have the opportunity to demonstrate their grasp and achievement of course objectives, their cognitive presence improves. Adroit facilitation of online conversation and discourse lays the path for more advanced student participation [57]. The teacher's well-nurtured presence in virtual class is critical to developing a community of learners to attain cognitive accomplishment.

To attain these goals, learners must emphasize self-efficacy, self-regulation, and a strong emphasis on inquiry [55]. As previously said, prior planning and preparation is an important predictor of student achievement. Even before the course begins, a teacher must foster student-student and student-teacher involvement. This engagement can be fostered by sending out welcome greetings, making weekly announcements, sharing photos or stories, and so on. Furthermore, social presence can be produced by including cultural elements into virtual classroom or VC such as a creative discussion forum and questions designed to elicit feedback and multiple responses.

Asynchronous online teaching necessitates extra work to build a presence and educational relationship with the teacher and among students, whereas traditional face-to-face learning incorporates the physical presence of the teacher. As the connecting aspect of cognitive and social presence, teaching presence brings together an online learning community and provides the cognitive and social activities essential for successful online learning [29]. Teachers who are proficient in teaching presence have the capacity to transform the learning experience from routine to exceptional. As a result, it is vital for English language learners to be in an online environment with a simulated and student-centered teaching presence that emphasizes learning that is both active and collaborative.

The CoI framework, as derived from research in various elements of language learning, is applicable with EFL instruction in a virtual learning environment. According to reports, the devices used to measure presence are accurate. Stewart [58] stated that the updated CoI Survey has a strong alignment to the specific context of online writing courses as a technique for measuring the extent to which students engage in online collaborative learning. According to a modified version of the 34-item CoI survey questionnaire, students in high blended (50% online) classes had higher levels of teaching presence, social presence, and cognitive presence than students in medium blended (33% online). The concept of CoI, derived from research on several aspects of language learning, is appropriate to EFL instruction in a virtual learning environment. According to reports, an analysis of survey responses paired with observations of assigned online activities reveals a correlation between online time on task and interactive learning activities that increase collaborative student-student interactions [59].

CoI framework is reported to enhance language skills in virtual collaborative learning [60] take for example, in writing [59], speaking [61]–[63] reading [64] and listening [65]. Furthermore, the framework fosters multiliteracies ability. Students have responded positively to an EFL course built in accordance with the framework of the CoI, which has greatly enhanced students' multiliteracies. The framework's cognitive and teacher-related features are especially beneficial to the development of multiliteracies [66].

CoI framework that necessitates shared meaning through interaction and collaboration is applicable in language learning that calls for interaction and collaboration both with teachers and among course participants. As previously stated by Swan [67], students' pleasure and perceived learning were significantly influenced by design clarity, involvement with teachers, and active conversation among students. In line with

this, Asoodar *et al.* [5] found that students were more satisfied with their virtual course discussions since they could share their knowledge and experience with their classmates. The students were also able to comprehend other people's points of view in a dynamic and appealing fashion, and they saw the flexibility of virtual classrooms as a benefit because they could log in at any time and from any location.

The CoI and critical thinking relationship paradigm revealed by Garrison *et al.* [13] was reviewed in [68], [69]. Golding [68], by using thought-provoking questions in a community of inquiry, students can develop critical characters and learn to speak, act, and think like expert critical thinkers. Meanwhile, Yang and Mohd [69] discovered that SP and TP had a positive effect on CP. According to the findings, critical thinking appears to be a positive mediator of the link between SP and CP, as well as TP and CP. greater CP is perceived by EFL university students who have greater SP, TP, and critical thinking levels. Finally, this study underlines the significance of critical thinking as a mechanism in the framework of CoI.

6. IMPLEMENTATION OF CoI FRAMEWORK IN TEFL IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

One of the most often utilized frameworks in online teaching and learning is the CoI framework [48]. However, research on the adoption of the CoI framework in secondary schools in general, and TEFL in particular, is lacking. Journal articles in this topic are hard to come by. K12 online learning research is trailing, which provides rich potential for scholars while also making it more difficult to discern patterns throughout the discipline [70]. The application of technology has been the focus of the majority of research on online remote learning at this level of education. As more and more elements of life become digitally mediated and pandemic-forced online, the necessity to handle online distance learning has grown. Despite its rarity, research show that CoI can be adapted for use in secondary school TEFL. According to Preece and Bularafa [60], the framework is an excellent way for teaching speaking abilities, and EFL teachers must master and apply the method to enhance language skills. Díaz and Miy [61] validated the existence of a TEFL framework in secondary schools and revealed that the presence of a teacher promotes grammar, correctness, and vocabulary. Research to meet these demands must be expanded. Collaboration with K-12 schools [49] corporations [49], and blended learning settings [51], [71] is welcomed. Furthermore, research on disciplinary distinctions utilizing the CoI framework is required. Replication and modification can assist you in developing a thorough understanding of the subject [52].

Despite the fact that the use of technology has been the primary focus of secondary school study, the research has yielded comparable findings of the need for new abilities rather than only the use of technology that can cater to students' engagement and collaboration. According to Pulham and Graham [71], the skills required to teach in online and blended environments differ from those required to teach in a traditional classroom. However, according to Moore-Adams *et al.* [72], most teacher preparation programs do not equip prospective teachers for new approaches of teaching. To accommodate this demand, teachers must be provided the chance to acquire the unique knowledge and skills required to teach online. Miller's study conclusion [73] demonstrates that distant learning reveals broken relationships. To demonstrate genuine caring and develop relatedness, teachers must act as warm demanders, respond to kids' social-emotional needs, and endeavor to bridge the digital gap. Finally, Sanders and Lokey-Vega [74]'s findings, which used a descriptive case study to investigate instructors' attitudes and practices in fully online classes, resulted in the K-12 CoI framework, which was named after them.

7. CONCLUSION

Although many studies show the CoI framework is a key predictor of learning success in virtual learning milieu, research on its implementation in EFL learning is still very rare. Over the past 10 years there have been only 27 studies that actually relate to its implementation in high schools. Those rare research reported that CoI framework was able to enhance language skills in a virtual learning environment. The EFL course prepared in accordance with the notion of the CoI was warmly appreciated by students and considerably enhanced students' multiliteracies. The rarity of the research in this field makes it potential for researchers to develop, replicate, or modify research to confirm the suitability, or to invent new model of this framework in EFL learning.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. G. Huber and C. Helm, "COVID-19 and schooling: evaluation, assessment and accountability in times of crises—reacting quickly to explore key issues for policy, practice and research with the school barometer," *Educational Assessment, Evaluation and Accountability*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 237–270, May 2020, doi: 10.1007/s11092-020-09322-y.
- [2] P. L. C. LAM, H. K. Y. NG, A. H. H. TSE, M. Lu, and B. Y. W. WONG, "eLearning technology and the advancement of practical constructivist pedagogies: Illustrations from classroom observations," *Education and Information Technologies*, vol. 26,

- no. 1, pp. 89–101, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1007/s10639-020-10245-w.
- [3] C. Coman, L. G. Țiru, L. Meseșan-Schmitz, C. Stanciu, and M. C. Bularca, "Online teaching and learning in higher education during the coronavirus pandemic: Students' perspective," *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, vol. 12, no. 24, pp. 1–22, 2020, doi: 10.3390/su122410367.
 - [4] A. Rasheed, R. A., Kamsin, A., "Challenges in the online component of blended learning," *A. ELSEVIER Computers & Education* 144, pp. 1–14, 2020.
 - [5] M. Asoodar, M. R. Atai, S. Vaezi, and S. S. Marandi, "Examining effectiveness of communities of practice in online English for academic purposes (EAP) assessment in virtual classes," *Computers & Education*, vol. 70, pp. 291–300, Jan. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2013.08.016.
 - [6] A. T. Tolu, "An Exploration of Synchronous Communication in an Online Preservice ESOL Course: Community of Inquiry Perspective," University of South Florida, 2010.
 - [7] S. M. Alavi and M. Taghizadeh, "Cognitive Presence in Virtual Learning Community: An EFL Case Résumé," *International Journal of e-Learning and Distance Education*, vol. 27, no. 1, 2013, [Online]. Available: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Cognitive-Presence-in-A-Virtual-Learning-Community%3A-Alavi-Taghizadeh/926fae860e2ff10d525cc244fa7738f045959b6b>.
 - [8] N. Arnold and L. Ducate, "Future foreign language teachers' social and cognitive collaboration in an online environment," *Language Learning and Technology*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 42–66, 2006.
 - [9] S. T. Chen, *Perceptions of online tesol teacher education: Strengths, weaknesses, characteristics, and effective components.*, vol. 73, no. 11-A(E). 2012.
 - [10] L. A. Olesova, J. C. Richardson, D. Weasenforth, and C. Meloni, "Using Asynchronous Instructional Audio Feedback in Online Environments: A Mixed Methods Study," *Jolt.Merlot.Org*, 2011. http://jolt.merlot.org/vol7no1/olesova_0311.htm (accessed Jul. 01, 2022).
 - [11] J. Song, "Redesigning a Foreign Language Class Based on the Community of Inquiry Model: Students' Learning Success and Satisfaction with an Online Course," *The Korean Language in America*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 29–54, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.5325/korelangamer.25.1.0029.
 - [12] A. N. Rachman, A. Maghfiroh, D. A. Mustikawati, and N. R. Indriastuti, "Community of Inquiry for Students' Autonomy in English Language Learning: A Case of Philippines High School," *IJELTAL (Indonesian Journal of English Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics)*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 61, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.21093/ijeltal.v6i1.849.
 - [13] D. R. Garrison, T. Anderson, and W. Archer, "Critical thinking, cognitive presence, and computer conferencing in distance education," *American Journal of Distance Education*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 7–23, Jan. 2001, doi: 10.1080/08923640109527071.
 - [14] D. H.-C. Cheung, A. K.-L. Ng, K.-M. Kiang, and H. H.-Y. Chan, "Creating a community of inquiry in the science classroom: an effective pedagogy for teaching diverse students?," *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 1–13, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1080/0309877X.2018.1491959.
 - [15] K. Swan, "Learning effectiveness online: What the research tells us," *Elements of Quality Online Education, Practice and Direction*, pp. 13–45, 2003, doi: 10.1111/j.1467-8535.2005.00519.x.
 - [16] D. R. Garrison and J. B. Arbaugh, "Researching the community of inquiry framework: Review, issues, and future directions," *The Internet and Higher Education*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 157–172, Jan. 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.iheduc.2007.04.001.
 - [17] D. González Miy and L. E. Herrera Díaz, "Tracking the Path of Communities of Inquiry in TEFL: A Literature Review," *HOW*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 80–94, Apr. 2015, doi: 10.19183/how.22.1.83.
 - [18] L. Harasim, "Online Collaborative Learning Theory (Harasim)," *December, 17, 2015*. <https://www.learning-theories.com/online-collaborative-learning-theory-harasim.html> (accessed Mar. 13, 2022).
 - [19] Z. Akyol *et al.*, "A Response to the Review of the Community of Inquiry Framework," *International Journal of E-Learning & Distance Education*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 123–136, 2009.
 - [20] D. R. Garrison, "Communities of Inquiry in Online Learning," in *Encyclopedia of Distance Learning, Second Edition*, IGI Global, 2009, pp. 352–355.
 - [21] E. Sung and R. E. Mayer, "Five facets of social presence in online distance education," *Computers in Human Behavior*, vol. 28, no. 5, pp. 1738–1747, Sep. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.chb.2012.04.014.
 - [22] D. R. Garrison, *E-Learning in the 21st Century*, 2nd ed. New York: Routledge, 2011.
 - [23] L. Dzubinski, "Teaching Presence: Co-Creating a Multi-National Online Learning Community in an Asynchronous Classroom," *Online Learning*, vol. 18, no. 2, Jun. 2014, doi: 10.24059/olj.v18i2.412.
 - [24] J. Bérešová, "An e-learning Course in EAP – Enhancing Academic Study Skills, Language and Culture," *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, vol. 174, pp. 3619–3624, Feb. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.1080.
 - [25] M. Malik, G. Fatima, A. Hussain Ch, and A. Sarwar, "E-Learning: Students' Perspectives about Asynchronous and Synchronous Resources at Higher Education Level," *Bulletin of Education and Research*, vol. 39, no. 2, pp. 183–195, 2017.
 - [26] D. L. DiPeri, "Exploring how curriculum can strengthen the oral communication skills of undergraduate online students," *ProQuest*, 2020. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/474b6ae1c0692a0a1983607d7a2cd27e/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y> (accessed Mar. 13, 2022).
 - [27] J. Shinge and S. Kotabagi, "To Improve Presentation Skills of the Engineering students through a Vis-à-vis Evaluation Approach - A Pedagogical Experiment," *Procedia Computer Science*, vol. 172, pp. 350–356, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2020.05.168.
 - [28] T. Anderson, L. Rourke, R. Garrison, and W. Archer, "Assessing Teaching Presence in a Computer Conferencing Context," *Online Learning*, vol. 5, no. 2, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.24059/olj.v5i2.1875.
 - [29] D. R. Garrison and M. Cleveland-Innes, "Facilitating Cognitive Presence in Online Learning: Interaction Is Not Enough," *American Journal of Distance Education*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 133–148, Sep. 2005, doi: 10.1207/s15389286ajde1903_2.
 - [30] K. A. Preisman, "Teaching Presence in Online Education: From the Instructor's Point-of-View," *Online Learning*, vol. 18, no. 3, Sep. 2014, doi: 10.24059/olj.v18i3.446.
 - [31] P. Shea, C. Sau Li, and A. Pickett, "A study of teaching presence and student sense of learning community in fully online and web-enhanced college courses," *The Internet and Higher Education*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 175–190, Jul. 2006, doi: 10.1016/j.iheduc.2006.06.005.
 - [32] P. C. Bernard, R. M., E. Abrami, Y. Lou, L. Borokhovski, A. Wade, M. Wozney, P.A. Wallet, Fiset, and B. Huang, "How does distance education compare with classroom instruction?," *Review of Educational Research*, vol. 74, no. 3, pp. 379–439, 2004.
 - [33] C. Baker, "The impact of instructor immediacy and presence for online student affective learning, cognition, and motivation," *Journal of Educators Online*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–30, 2010, doi: 10.9743/JEO.2010.1.2.
 - [34] T. Mcaleavy and K. Gorgen, "What does the research suggest is best practice in pedagogy for remote teaching?," *Education Development Trust*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 1–26, 2020.
 - [35] R. Tirado-Morueta, P. Maraver-López, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, and Á. Hernando-Gómez, "Exploring Social Network Structure

- Patterns Suitable to the Community of Inquiry Model Moderated by the Task,” *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, vol. 58, no. 2, pp. 319–342, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.1177/0735633119845695.
- [36] S. Stenbom, “A systematic review of the Community of Inquiry survey,” *The Internet and Higher Education*, vol. 39, pp. 22–32, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.iheduc.2018.06.001.
- [37] J. M. Zydney, A. DeNoyelles, and K. Kyeong-Ju Seo, “Creating a community of inquiry in online environments: An exploratory study on the effect of a protocol on interactions within asynchronous discussions,” *Computers & Education*, vol. 58, no. 1, pp. 77–87, Jan. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2011.07.009.
- [38] H. S. Fiock, “Designing a Community of Inquiry in Online Courses,” *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 112–133, 2020, doi: 10.19173/irrodl.v20i5.4383.
- [39] L. Cifuentes, “The Perfect Online Course: Best Practices for Designing and Teaching Anymir Orellana, Terry L. Hudgins, and Michael Simonson, Eds.,” *American Journal of Distance Education*, vol. 24, no. 3, pp. 171–173, Aug. 2010, doi: 10.1080/08923647.2010.497011.
- [40] J. B. Arbaugh *et al.*, “Developing a community of inquiry instrument: Testing a measure of the Community of Inquiry framework using a multi-institutional sample,” *The Internet and Higher Education*, vol. 11, no. 3–4, pp. 133–136, Jan. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.iheduc.2008.06.003.
- [41] E. Gutiérrez-Santiuste, C. Rodríguez-Sabiote, and M.-J. Gallego-Arrufat, “Cognitive presence through social and teaching presence in communities of inquiry: A correlational–predictive study,” *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, vol. 31, no. 3, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.14742/ajet.1666.
- [42] S. Lin, T.-C. Hung, and C.-T. Lee, “Revalidate Forms of Presence in Training Effectiveness,” *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 32–54, Sep. 2015, doi: 10.1177/0735633115588772.
- [43] L. Rourke and H. Kanuka, “Learning in Communities of Inquiry: A Review of the Literature.,” *Journal of Distance Education*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 19–48, 2009, [Online]. Available: <http://eric.ed.gov.ezproxy.bethel.edu/?id=EJ836030>.
- [44] P. Shea *et al.*, “A re-examination of the community of inquiry framework: Social network and content analysis,” *The Internet and Higher Education*, vol. 13, no. 1–2, pp. 10–21, Jan. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.iheduc.2009.11.002.
- [45] M. Cleveland-Innes and P. Campbell, “Emotional presence, learning, and the online learning environment,” *International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 269–292, 2012, doi: 10.19173/irrodl.v13i4.1234.
- [46] J. Y. C. Lam, “Autonomy presence in the extended community of inquiry,” *International Journal of Continuing Education and Lifelong Learning*, vol. 8, no. 1, p. 39, 2015, [Online]. Available: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Autonomy-presence-in-the-extended-community-of-Lam/bb4a48c9e0b2ddd4c592e4c19df06671d5651276>.
- [47] K. Kozan and S. Caskurlu, “On the Nth presence for the Community of Inquiry framework,” *Computers & Education*, vol. 122, pp. 104–118, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2018.03.010.
- [48] S. K. Jan, P. Vlachopoulos, and M. Parsell, “Social Network Analysis and Online Learning Communities in Higher Education: A Systematic Literature Review,” *Online Learning*, vol. 23, no. 1, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.24059/olj.v23i1.1398.
- [49] K. B. Harrell and J. L. Wendt, “The Impact of Blended Learning on Community of Inquiry and Perceived Learning among High School Learners Enrolled in a Public Charter School,” *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 259–272, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1080/15391523.2019.1590167.
- [50] L. Bage, “Satisfaction with online learning options in the insurance industry: Does mindfulness play a role,” Ph.D. dissertation, University of Pennsylvania, 2018.
- [51] H. Duncan and J. Barnett, “Learning to teach online: What works for pre-service teachers,” *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 357–376, 2009, doi: 10.2190/EC.40.3.f.
- [52] J. C. Richardson, J. Ben Arbaugh, M. Cleveland-Innes, P. Ice, K. P. Swan, and D. R. Garrison, “Using the Community of Inquiry Framework to Inform Effective Instructional Design,” in *The Next Generation of Distance Education*, Boston, MA: Springer US, 2012, pp. 97–125.
- [53] J. G. Sallán, “Las comunidades virtuales de aprendizaje,” pp. 41–64, 2006. [Online] Available: <https://raco.cat/index.php/Educar/article/view/58020/68088>.
- [54] D. Castellanos-Reyes, “20 Years of the Community of Inquiry Framework,” *TechTrends*, vol. 64, no. 4, pp. 557–560, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s11528-020-00491-7.
- [55] P. Shea and T. Bidjerano, “Learning presence: Towards a theory of self-efficacy, self-regulation, and the development of a communities of inquiry in online and blended learning environments,” *Computers & Education*, vol. 55, no. 4, pp. 1721–1731, Dec. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2010.07.017.
- [56] M.-N. Lamy and R. Hampel, “Teaching Online,” in *Online Communication in Language Learning and Teaching*, London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2007, pp. 61–75.
- [57] R. P. K. Palloff, *The Excellent Online Instructor: Strategies for Professional Development*. San Francisco: John Wiley & Sons, 2011.
- [58] M. K. Stewart, “The Community of Inquiry Survey: An Assessment Instrument for Online Writing Courses,” *Computers and Composition*, vol. 52, pp. 37–52, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.compcom.2019.01.001.
- [59] M. K. Stewart, L. Hilliard, N. Stillman-Webb, and J. M. Cunningham, “The Community of Inquiry in Writing Studies Survey: Interpreting Social Presence in Disciplinary Contexts,” *Online Learning*, vol. 25, no. 2, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.24059/olj.v25i2.2275.
- [60] A. S. D. Preece and M. W. Bularafa, “Community of inquiry method and language skills acquisition: empirical evidence,” *Journal of Education and Practice*, vol. 6, no. 27, pp. 89–93, 2015, [Online]. Available: <http://irep.iium.edu.my/62716/>.
- [61] L. E. Herrera Díaz and D. González Miy, “Developing the Oral Skill in Online English Courses Framed by the Community of Inquiry,” *PROFILE Issues in Teachers’ Professional Development*, vol. 19, no. 1, p. 73, 2017, doi: 10.15446/profile.v19n1.55957.
- [62] E. Solimani, A. Ameri-Golestan, and A. Lotfi, “Flipped vs. unplugged instructions: Sailing EFL learners’ oral proficiency through virtual and real learning communities,” *International Journal of Instruction*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 459–480, 2019, doi: 10.29333/iji.2019.12328a.
- [63] W. C. V. Wu, J. S. C. Hsieh, and J. C. Yang, “Creating an online learning community in a flipped classroom to enhance efl learners’ oral proficiency,” *Educational Technology and Society*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 142–157, 2017.
- [64] F. Sari, “Enhancing Students Reading Ability Through Inquiry Based Learning To Efl Students,” *English Community Journal*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 60–64, 2017, doi: 10.32502/ecj.v1i1.653.
- [65] M. W. Bularafa, “The Use of Community of Inquiry Method To Develop ESL Learners’ Speaking Skill,” 2016. <https://lib.iium.edu.my/mom/services/mom/document/getFile/3zOHYzB5kQ2DtBjnkKml7wAb71fi3kNA20170314105719859>.
- [66] D. Zhang and Y. Zou, “Fostering Multiliteracies Through Blended EFL Learning,” *International Journal of Linguistics, Literature and Translation*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 40–48, 2020, doi: 10.32996/ijllt.2020.3.2.5.

- [67] K. Swan, "Virtual interaction: Design factors affecting student satisfaction and perceived learning in asynchronous online courses," *Distance Education*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 306–331, Jan. 2001, doi: 10.1080/0158791010220208.
- [68] C. Golding, "Educating for critical thinking: thought-encouraging questions in a community of inquiry," *Higher Education Research & Development*, vol. 30, no. 3, pp. 357–370, Jun. 2011, doi: 10.1080/07294360.2010.499144.
- [69] L. Yang and R. B. S. Mohd, "The relationship between critical thinking and the community of inquiry model: a quantitative study among EFL university students in China," *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 965–973, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.1080/02673843.2020.1814359.
- [70] J. D. Basham and M. T. Marino, "Understanding STEM Education and Supporting Students through Universal Design for Learning," *Teaching Exceptional Children*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 8–15, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1177/004005991304500401.
- [71] E. Pulham and C. R. Graham, "Comparing K-12 online and blended teaching competencies: a literature review," *Distance Education*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 411–432, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1080/01587919.2018.1476840.
- [72] B. L. Moore-Adams, W. M. Jones, and J. Cohen, "Learning to teach online: a systematic review of the literature on K-12 teacher preparation for teaching online," *Distance Education*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 333–348, Sep. 2016, doi: 10.1080/01587919.2016.1232158.
- [73] K. E. Miller, "A Light in Students' Lives: K-12 Teachers' Experiences (Re)Building Caring Relationships During Remote Learning," *Online Learning*, vol. 25, no. 1, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.24059/olj.v25i1.2486.
- [74] K. Sanders and A. Lokey-Vega, "K-12 Community of Inquiry: A case study of the applicability of the Community of Inquiry framework in the K-12 online learning environment," *Journal of Online Learning Research*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 35–56, 2020.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Suharno is a faculty member of English Education Study Program, Faculty of Language and Literature Education, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Bandung, Indonesia. He is also a doctor candidate of school of post graduate at the same university. He has extensively experienced in teaching in various levels of education, from primary to tertiary, formal, and non-formal education. He has written English textbooks published by CV Arya Duta, UPI Press, and Pusurbuk/center of curriculum and book, Ministry of National Education. His research interest is in EFL methodology, ESP, ICT and distance learning pedagogy. He can be reached at email: suharno@upi.edu.

Didi Suherdi is a professor of Education at English Education Study Program School of Post Graduate Study, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Bandung, Indonesia. He has extensive national and international publications in the area of English teaching methodology. He also has done numerous research and published books relatable to his expertise. He is currently the head of English Education Program of School of Post Graduate of the Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia. He is also an assessor of AUN QA (ASEAN University Network Quality Assurance). He can be reached via email: suherdi_d@upi.edu.

Wawan Gunawan is a holder of master and PhD in literary education from University of Queensland, Australia and University of Massachusetts, USA respectively. He is currently a faculty member, a lecturer at English Education Study Program School of Post Graduate Study, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia, Bandung, Indonesia. He has extensively published his research in various national and international journals. He also has disseminated his research in systemic functional linguistics in seminars and conferences. He can be reached at wagoen@upi.edu.